

DESIGNING FROM GRANDMOTHERS DOMESTICITY IN BOGOTA

METHODOLOGIES AND PROCESSES

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ABSTRACT

The future cannot be understood without the past, without the traditions and without those tangible and intangible legacies that bind us emotionally to a place. In this lies the beauty that connects people with the objects that surround them and the spaces they live in.

From the study of the objects and the poetic and aesthetic aspects of grandmothers' houses in Bogotá, a proposal of both a location and various objects is developed. The proposal is an approach to a domesticity in which the role of gender and narratives of Manuel Carreño's traditional book *Manual de urbanidad y buenas maneras* (Manual of Civility and Good Manners) become the axis for creating this place of conversation between emotions, tradition and design.

KEY WORDS: *traditions, poetic descriptions, domesticity, customs, Bogotá*

INTRODUCTION

The places, their traditions and rituals contain codes, which make people connect emotionally with the tangible and intangible elements which are part of a culture. In this document a description is given of the observational methodologies that allowed us to map and evaluate the characteristics of grandmothers' houses in Bogotá. A study of the methodologies of identification of elements and their translation into a design language can also be found. Stories and interactions at the dinner table are analyzed to create an object and space proposal that poses a place where traditions and emotions materialize.

VISUAL ETHNOGRAPHY APPLIED TO THE SEARCH OF DESIGN CONCEPTS

This project started with the exploration of Bogotá houses, citizens, and what defines their domesticity. Various categories of houses to observe were established, within which the houses of Bogotá grandmothers were defined as objects of considerable study, as they are containers of memory, tradition and rituals that define important features to understand domesticity in Bogotá.

The starting point in the observation was a workshop in which a group of people, mostly art and design students, were asked to search in their family homes for a number of objects that reminded them of the emotional interactions of the houses' inhabitants with their respective spaces, objects, situations

and specific rituals. These aspects were established from an observation guide and compilation of information (Mosse, 2010). This guide allowed to gather aspects relating to the most special places in the houses, their spiritual centers, the more or less important objects, the main sources of light, people who lived there and their meeting centers, the newest and oldest objects in the houses, and the special rituals that take place there. From the observed aspects, a sensitive framework was created, to be able to recognize what it is that connects people with their houses, meaning that they are not just places that contain physical aspects related with design, materials, areas, etc., but that they also contain emotional aspects in the way they are inhabited and appropriated.

The compilation tool that was used is known as Visual Ethnography, employed by visual anthropology to obtain information through photography and video, on the manifestations of a culture "through its visible symbols embedded in gestures, ceremonies, rituals and artifacts located in built or natural environments" (Ruby, 1996).

- 1 The Soft Domesticity Workshop took place in Bogotá on February 2010. Carolina Agudelo, Coordinator of Textiles and Fashion area at Universidad de los Andes' Design Department, and Carole Collet, Deputy Director of the Textile Futures Research Centre of University of the Arts, London, directed it. The workshop's aims were to collect visual information of Bogotá homes and to explore the possibilities for textiles in a future scenario for Bogotá in 2050. Twenty people participated and approximately 60 houses/homes were explored and documented for the workshop.

Figure 1. Grandmothers home conceptual map/moodboard. Photography: Juanda Contreras + Daniel Pinilla. 2013.

Once the information was gathered, a map was organized based on the spaces that were repeated more often in the collected photographs. That was how the garden, the entrance, the lounge, the dining room, the kitchen, the inner courtyard, the hall, the rooms and other spaces were mapped. This map was denominated Moodboard, which, in the creation of a project, is used to develop concepts and allow the Creative Director and his team to understand the visual style that has to be achieved. A poetic description of each space, based on the information collected, gave way to the conceptualization process. This poetic descriptions are the base of the project's concept; they are linked with the story or feeling captured in the images. These images often relate to family background, particular events, different feelings, materials, people or places. Their highly emotional content can be an input to create stories, therefore creating a link between image and word.

CONCEPT PROTOTYPING TO ESTABLISH THE AESTHETICS OF A DESIGN PROJECT

The concept prototyping was built based on points of interest taken from the conceptual map of grandmothers' houses. This tool uses the previously developed aesthetic language to analyze and translate visual and conceptual information from new images. This construction is made from the designer's or creator's particular interest, in a synthesis and appropriation exercise. Therefore this tool is highly influenced by the creator's personal sensitivity and emotion as well as the project's specific needs. This methodology is used by trends development offices to establish the aesthetic precepts on which an industry will move years in advance.

Some points of interest were taken from the grandmothers' houses related to situations and rituals identified as repetitive from the information collected from interviews to the inhabitants of the homes observed during the workshop. Those situations and rituals were intended to be explored for the final purpose of the project.

The concepts developed from these points were:

- 1 *Spiritual Collector*: The faith and spiritual corners of grandmothers' houses in Bogotá. It has to do with the Catholic religion that most of the homes in Bogotá profess. Religion as a way of expressing spirituality.

Figure 2. Grandmothers home concepts prototyping. Photography: Luisa Rodríguez. 2010

- 2 *Glazed Tile with Sunday Flavor and Sunday Break*: The weekend meals prepared and set by the grandmother for her family. They become a meeting and behavioral ritual.
- 3 *Objects from a Withheld Past*: the most meaningful or antique objects that are, in their great majority, provided with stories and anecdotes.
- 4 *Rustic Silver Reflection*: Cabinets full of silver objects that play an important role in the materiality of Bogotá homes.
- 5 *Souvenirs of a Walked Road*: The small objects that contain stories or are themselves a story. Memories that remain hidden from the quotidian view in form of a secret.
- 6 *Cuddling Memories and Handmade Lifestyle*: Presence of fabrics and crochet as a work of grandmothers. Houses are wrapped in fabrics.

Amber Tableware: The tableware that is used only for guests and special events. It regularly came as a wedding gift from some European country and is visible but not reachable, as a sort of treasure.

SCENARIO BUILDING FROM A SPECIFIC NARRATIVE

For each one of the concepts a scenario visualization was made, that results from an exercise of collecting design models and doing several brainstorming sessions, in which keyword lists were developed concerning the interactions, compositions, materials, and narratives that the concepts express. Each of these scenarios was named and organized in an infographic for further analysis.

To continue the development of the project, the concept *Amber Tableware* was chosen because several of the answers in the questionnaires made during the visual ethnography situated the ritual around the table and the food, as one of the most important ones practiced in grandmothers' homes in Bogota.

This suggested a point of intersection between generations, the emotional connection provided by a meal; the table dressed and fine tableware are the points on which the ritual rotates.

The scenario built for this concept was established around the narrative about manners and behavior at the table and is guided by the book *Manual de urbanidad y buenas maneras* (Manual of Civility and Good Manners) of Manuel Carreño, published in the year 1853. Houses of grandmothers are the most traditional homes in urban Bogotá, becoming the last place where we can still find traditions and ways of behaving inherited from the nineteenth century. As a result of these influences, especially the English and the Victorian ones, the book traditionally known as *La urbanidad de Carreño* appeared in some South American countries (in the past part of the Gran Colombia, which included Venezuela, Colombia, Panama and Ecuador, some parts of Brazil, Perú and Nicaragua). The book was used in Colombia up until the 1970's, and was used as the guidebook to educate generations on how to behave in society. This traditional book was chosen for the development of the narrative of the scenario because it was a reference of good manners for many of Bogotá's citizens. *La urbanidad de Carreño* has a chapter dedicated to behavior and etiquette at the table, from which the elements for the food ritual scenario development were extracted. The narrative of the scenario was named "The space of good manners, the objects of good customs".

These elements laid down the stage narrative into three phases: the table set up, the moment during the meal and the moment after the meal. An analysis was made in these three phases, about three elements that contain the insights on which the project's design phase was developed: the roles, the objects and the space. The roles established by Carreño were crucial to find out the relationships between the protagonists of the scenario and the elements of their story, for each of the project's pieces. For instance, the hostess, who is the lady of the house, is the reference point for the distribu-

Figure 3. Grandmothers home scenarios. Infographics: Jaime Patarroyo. 2012.

Figure 4. Amber china scenario / "The space of good manners, the objects of good customs". Infographic: Jaime Patarroyo. 2012.

Figure 5A. Table rituals infographic. Infographic: Lina Giraldo + Valentina Danna. 2012

Figure 5B. Objects, roles and spaces infographic. Infographic: Lina Giraldo + Valentina Danna. 2012

tion of the different dinner guests at a table according to their level of importance. Objects that are part of the ritual play an important role in the way the dinner is served, the use of the utensils and the appropriate limit in the gestures and behaviors at the table. The space defines the paths and interactions between one guest and another.

THE MATERIALIZATION OF THE SPACE OF GOOD MANNERS, THE OBJECTS OF GOOD CUSTOMS

From the infographics and the identified and declared elements, a design place was marked out. Therefore, it could be defined that a confined space (the floor) was needed, a central object for the ritual (the table), some objects in which the ritual's participants could be located (the chairs) and the elements to prepare the ritual and set up the table (the tableware).

Figure 6. Sketches and prototypes. Photography: Santiago Orjuela + Jaime Patarroyo. 2012

Figure 7. Space prototype and final lacy floor. Photography: Carolina Agudelo. 2012-2013

The Space

To be able to understand the space, a prototype was made to get a feel of the scale that the project's staging would finally have. With wooden boxes, the size of the space was established. It was already clear from an earlier sketching that a floor would limit the space. The floor was finally developed based on a piece of lace from the seventeenth century and ceramics were intervened and translated into a giant tablecloth. The lace is important within the materiality defined from the concept prototype. It is highly ornate, it denotes a woman's table and it forms part of the world of crochet and lace, found repeatedly in different scenarios of grandmothers' houses in Bogotá.

The Chairs

The design process and materialization of the chairs had to do with the people that would be seated on them and that, according to the ritual, are: the hostess or lady of the house, the gentleman of the house, the important couple of guests, and the not so important couple of guests. In this way the search for the chairs started. They would translate the social features and behavior from those who were going to seat at the table depending on their degree of importance. The process of sketching was done with the chairs to emphasize features and characteristics of the table's characters. The chairs of the host and hostess or gentleman and lady of the house have a common gesture: they are long and squared. The gentleman's has a heavy gesture whereas the lady's one is much lighter.

Figure 8A. Lady's chair. Photography: Juanda Contreras. 2013.

The chairs of the important guests are rounded and decorated on top with an ornate carving. The chairs were joined in a gesture that determines the dominance of men over women at the stage of defining the positions in the table and other aspects of their lives⁹.

The chairs of the non important guests are simpler, also rounded but with less ornaments. They were also joined with the same gesture of men over women. The chair is uncomfortable, showing the hostess' indifference for the guests' comfort, it has the seat tilted forward pushing the guest onto the table and forcing him to use his legs for support.

Figure 8B. Gentleman's chair. Photography: Juanda Contreras. 2013.

- 2 For some people the book *La urbanidad de Carreño* appears at times extremely sexist and controlling in reference to women's activities and gestures. Considering it was written in 1850, it is understood that women's freedom was restricted by male figures, father or husband.

Figure 9. Important guests' chair. Photography: Juanda Contreras. 2013.

Figure 10. Unimportant guests' chair. Photography: Juanda Contreras. 2013.

Figure 11. Table. Photography: Juanda Contreras. 2013.

Figure 12. Tableware. Photography: Juanda Contreras. 2013.

The Table

The table was a fortunate discovery. In the quest for a piece that would fit the size of the originally developed prototype, it was found in a warehouse in a city near Bogotá. The table was not intervened or modified. It was finished and painted and presented that way.

The Tableware

In the same way as the chairs, each set of the tableware was developed taking into account the characteristics of the guests and the narrative imposed on each one of them.

For the prototype, paper traditional lace table covers were used, that were part of the materiality of the constructed scenario. White standard tableware was used as the base, and for the design, instructions from La Urbanidad de Carreño were taken, and thus, the borders were ornamented so that the food would not touch them, precise instructions for the use of the cutlery and where it should rest after eating were written, a tilted soup bowl was made and plates were made as baskets where only one loaf of bread would fit. From these prototypes, the ceramic dishes were made, taking paper lace onto different materials distant from flexibility, that despite being heavy and rigid, achieved a feeling of lightness.

The Space of Good Manners, the Objects of Good Customs: Installation Artwork

Figure 13A. Installation. Photography: Juanda Contreras. 2013.

COMPILATION OF METHODOLOGIES

Some methodologies related to fields as design, arts and social sciences were applied through the development of the project.

Visual ethnography was used to obtain first hand information about homes in Bogotá and their domesticity. From all the images collected that contained sensible and emotional information it was possible to build visual maps that are known as moodboards. A moodboard is a tool use by designers to communicate their ideas effectively through the development of a project. Conceptual maps, that in this project are the conceptual conclusion of moodboards, were built from the answers obtained from the questionnaires done during the visual ethnography. Those answers related with sensations of the images selected conclude in phrases used to name them.

Concept prototyping is the appropriation of aesthetic concepts to be reinterpreted and presented from the particular interest of the project. All those images constructed become the starting point from which different design scenarios were built. The scenario building was made from the insights, referents and narratives compiled to communicate the concept values effectively. To visualize the conclusions of the scenarios, infographics were developed as a visual conclusion to establish the most important and definite ideas in the development of the project

The construction of narratives around the concepts was a crucial task for the project. Through stories it was possible to design around poetry, relating it to recover traditions and the way people will relate to them in the future. There was emotional information that was fundamental to the narrative behind the pieces and the space. From narratives and scenarios it was possible to make sketches and fast prototypes to materialize ideas. Forms, sizes, colors, textures, materials and interactions were established and evaluated to decide what pieces to develop for the project. Material experimentation was fundamental to be able to push the materials forward and is made through an animated conversation within materials at laboratories and workshops with crafters involved. In this project the rigid materials become softer in appearances because of those conversations.

Figure 13B. Installation. Photography: Carolina Agudelo. 2013.

The definition of materials and the making of final prototypes are the final phase of the project, giving an accurate idea of what was explored and the decisions made in each one of the phases developed.

CONCLUSIONS

This project begins with a sensitive and emotional journey to the places where we live as citizens of Bogotá, places that contain traditions and rituals passed down from generation to generation, and aesthetic codes that make us feel at home.

One of the main objectives of the project is to create a map of the tools and methodologies that we use as designers and artists in creation processes. Those methodologies we use in decision-making that are carried out in a sensitive way, but that also correspond to the tangible needs of a project, such as choosing a color or material. Many of these tools, taken from sciences and social sciences, translated to a sensitive perspective, make creation in design and art an interesting place where rationality and emotion converge.

This project celebrates the development of objects that spin a story of meanings surrounding the ritual of food. It is based on a book of manners that, although currently out of date, contains information on our culture and permits us to connect with a past that gives us inputs to define our present and future materiality, in a celebration of local customs we can project to the world.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

“The Space of Good Manners, the Objects of Good Customs” was a research project developed under the FAPA (APSF Assistant Professor Support Fund) at the Design Department of Universidad de los Andes, Bogotá. I would like to thank Lucía Tejeiro and Catalina Manotas for their help in copyediting and translating this document. Thanks to all our grandmothers because through them we are connected with traditions and good manners.

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